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Report on all Public Challenge activities

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Change Log

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Acronyms and Abbreviations

AI	Artificial Intelligence
BMZ	BioImage Model Zoo
D	Deliverable
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
GECI	Genetically Encoded Calcium Indicators
OC	Open Call(s)
PSNR	Peak Signal-to-Noise Ratio
SNR	Signal-to-Noise Ratio
SSIM	Structural Similarity Index Measure
v	Version
WP	Work Package

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Executive Summary

This deliverable reports on the AI4Life Public Challenge activities conducted within WP6 (Open Calls and Challenges) throughout the project.

The AI4Life Challenges were conceived as a way to bridge real-world imaging problems and the computer vision and deep learning communities to advance the state-of-the-art methods and create an open, reproducible benchmarking.

Initially, the project intended to source Challenge problems from the AI4Life Open Calls. However, early experience revealed several limitations, such as insufficient or low-quality datasets. These lessons motivated a shift toward designing challenges around broadly relevant, high-impact problems identified across multiple Open Call Submissions, focusing on image restoration and denoising.

Three challenges were organised during the reporting period:

1. Unsupervised Denoising Challenge (May–August 2024): Benchmarking denoising methods without ground truth references using synthetic and real microscopy datasets.
2. Supervised Denoising Challenge (June–August 2025): Evaluating methods trained on paired noisy/clean microscopy images.
3. Calcium Imaging Denoising Challenge (July–August 2025): Assessing algorithms for preserving temporal dynamics in neuroscience data.

Challenges were hosted on the [Grand Challenge](#) platform to ensure robust technical infrastructure, reproducible evaluation, and visibility within the wider community. These activities strengthened collaboration between bioimage analysis and machine learning experts, produced openly available benchmarks, and informed future best practices for challenge design in life sciences AI.

1. Introduction

The AI4Life project is part of the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme, led by the project coordinator Euro-BioImaging and participated in by 10 partners, 5 of them being European Research Infrastructures. The project started in September 2022 and will end in August 2025.

AI4Life aims to bring state-of-the-art AI-based image analysis to life scientists by establishing and supporting innovative services targeting researchers in the life sciences and computational methods developers in AI and computer vision.

More specifically, the objectives of AI4Life are

- **Objective 1: Democratised availability of AI-based image analysis methods** as a FAIR service accessible through the AI4Life service landscape and computationally powered by the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) infrastructure.
- **Objective 2: Establish standards** for the submission, storage, and FAIR access of reference data, reference annotations (ground-truth), trained AI models, and trainable AI methods.
- **Objective 3: Simple model deployment, sharing, and dissemination** of AI-based methods as a new developer-facing service of the [BioImage Model Zoo \(BMZ\)](#).
- **Objective 4: Organise Open Calls and Challenges** for outstanding image analysis.
- **Objective 5: Empower common image analysis platforms with AI tools.**
- **Objective 6: Organise outreach and training events.**

This deliverable is part of WP6, *Open Calls and Challenges*. WP6 contributes to Objective 4 by organising public Challenges and raising awareness of AI4Life and the opportunities it offers to life scientists.

2. Description of work

2.1 Structure of AI4Life Challenges

This deliverable describes how we structured the challenge program, including how tasks, datasets, and platforms were selected, and how we supported participants throughout.

2.1.1 Challenges and Open Calls

The initial plan, as outlined during the proposal phase of AI4Life, was to identify relevant image analysis problems through the Open Calls and then organise challenges based on the submitted image analysis problems and datasets. The goal was to spotlight these problems for the broader computer science and deep learning communities, allowing for direct benchmarking of existing methods and potentially inspiring the development of novel ones.

However, as the project progressed, we encountered several limitations:

1. **Overestimation of data quantity and readiness.** During project selection, we explicitly asked applicants whether they had sufficient labelled data for deep learning. However, in practice, many datasets proved unusable. Some datasets lacked necessary granularity, e.g., contained only centre points of objects when full segmentation masks were needed, while others were far smaller than claimed. More broadly, many applicants underestimated the volume and quality of data needed to train deep learning models.
2. **Excessive domain specificity.** Many proposals addressed highly specialised topics within subfields of biological imaging. While scientifically relevant, their narrow scope limited the broader relevance and cross-disciplinary, *i.e.*, bridging the life sciences and computer science, value of the potential Open Challenges.
3. **Difficulty translating problems into a challenge format.** Several proposals described complex experimental contexts or multi-step workflows that were hard to abstract into a single, well-defined computational task, which is essential for building effective and accessible challenges.

Overall, while the Open Calls provided valuable insight into real-world needs, they also revealed key practical and conceptual barriers to establishing challenges directly from them.

2.1.2 Task selection

Given the limitations of sourcing challenges directly from Open Call submissions, we adjusted our approach. Across many applications, we observed a recurring structure in the image analysis pipelines, typically involving the following steps:

1. Image preprocessing and image restoration – primarily denoising.
2. Image segmentation.
3. Downstream analysis and quantification.

While segmentation remains a key step, state-of-the-art tools such as *Cellpose* and *StarDist* already perform robustly on many common biological imaging tasks. Downstream analysis, by contrast, tends to be highly project-specific, making it difficult to define general-purpose challenges.

Image restoration, particularly denoising, stood out as a more broadly applicable and impactful task. Effective denoising not only improves the accuracy of subsequent steps (e.g., segmentation and quantification) but also enables the use of lower-quality or lower-signal data, which is often the reality in biological imaging.

We therefore identified a strong need within the community for better denoising methods and, crucially, for systematic benchmarking of existing approaches across diverse sample types and imaging modalities.

2.1.3 Dataset selection

To support our benchmarking goals, we made the decision to limit challenge data to existing and synthetic datasets. This decision was driven by three key considerations:

1. High-quality new data is difficult to obtain within short timelines. Acquiring novel datasets suitable for deep learning requires extensive annotation and validation workflows, which are time and resource-intensive, often exceeding the scope of challenge planning.
2. Data submissions to the Open Calls lacked sufficient quality or volume. The datasets provided by the Open Call participants were either too limited in scope, poorly annotated, or not ready for direct use in machine learning pipelines.
3. Existing datasets already cover relevant biological domains. Many publicly available datasets, as well as procedurally generated synthetic data, offer representative coverage of common imaging modalities and biological structures. They provide a practical and controlled foundation for designing robust, comparative challenges.

This approach allowed us to prioritise benchmarking feasibility and reproducibility, while still ensuring biological relevance.

2.1.4 Hosting platform selection

Hosting a deep learning challenge requires robust infrastructure for dataset management, solution submission, automated evaluation, and public leaderboards. Several well-established platforms widely recognised in the deep learning community are offering these features. Recreating this infrastructure in-house would have required significant technical effort and ongoing maintenance.

Moreover, these platforms provide built-in visibility and access to a large, engaged user base, factors that are especially important when aiming to connect bioimage analysis problems with the broader machine learning community.

After a comprehensive evaluation, we selected [Grand Challenge](#), a European platform specialising in medical imaging challenges. Although no existing platform focuses exclusively on biological imaging, the Grand Challenge offered the closest alignment with our needs. Their emphasis on medical imaging, support for reproducible solution packaging via Docker, competitive pricing, and European data compliance made them a strong strategic fit.

This partnership provided both the technical infrastructure and community alignment necessary to launch a high-quality, reproducible challenge without diverting resources toward platform development.

2.1.5 Organisation process

The organisation of each challenge followed a structured process:

1. **Defining a concrete and achievable task.** The selected task had to be precisely scoped and easily understandable to participants without a background in bioimage analysis.
2. **Selecting appropriate datasets.** Datasets were chosen to meet several criteria: sufficient size for training deep learning models, alignment with the challenge objective, inclusion of diverse imaging modalities, and representation of various biological sample types.
3. **Preparing comprehensive documentation for participants.** Each challenge included a dedicated set of informational pages covering: the scientific motivation and goals, detailed data descriptions, instructions for accessing and working with the datasets, links to relevant literature, and a clear guide on how to submit solutions via the hosting platform.
4. **Providing starter code and packaging instructions.** To facilitate participation, we released template code and instructions for packaging submissions using Docker. While not intended as a strong baseline for performance, these materials offered a starting point for participants to understand the expected format and workflow.

5. **Providing ongoing technical support.** We provided assistance to participants, helping with submission troubleshooting, clarification of task requirements, and practical guidance related to the challenge infrastructure.

Through this process, we aimed to build challenges that were both robust and approachable, fostering collaboration between the deep learning and bioimage communities

2.2 Description of the conducted challenges

The challenges conducted under AI4Life were shaped by both strategic objectives and the practical constraints identified in Section 2.1. From here, we provide an overview of each individual challenge along with its organisation and key details.

2.2.1. Challenge 1: Unsupervised Denoising

2.2.1.1 Challenge description

The first AI4Life Challenge focused on unsupervised denoising – an approach especially valuable in microscopy, where generating clean/noisy image pairs is often impractical. Participants were invited to apply deep learning models to two types of noise – structured (e.g., pixel-correlated artifacts from confocal or fluorescence microscopy) and unstructured (e.g., Gaussian or Poisson noise from imaging detectors).

In collaboration with *Alexander Krull* (University of Birmingham, UK), a researcher in the field and external to the AI4Life consortium, we assembled four distinct datasets – two featuring structured noise and two featuring unstructured noise. The challenge ran from early May through August 2024. Participants submitted their algorithms packaged as Docker containers, which were evaluated automatically. All participants were encouraged to release their code publicly, which was mandatory for the top three participants.

The challenge description can be found on the following two websites:

- <https://ai4life-mdc24.grand-challenge.org/>, and
- <https://ai4life.eurobioimaging.eu/denoising-challenge/>.

2.2.1.2 Challenge results

The challenge attracted 104 registrants from 27 countries worldwide and received 151 submissions. The results are published here on the following website: <https://ai4life-mdc24.grand-challenge.org/results/>.

2.2.2. Challenge 2: Supervised Denoising

2.2.2.1 Challenge description

The challenge can be accessed using the following link: <https://ai4life-mdc25.grand-challenge.org/>

The AI4Life Microscopy Supervised Denoising Challenge 2025 builds on the success of our 2024 unsupervised denoising challenge, this time shifting the focus to supervised deep learning approaches. In supervised denoising, models are trained on paired noisy and clean images, allowing them to learn explicit mappings from degraded inputs to their high-quality counterparts. This enables more accurate and reliable noise removal compared to unsupervised approaches, where no ground truth reference exists.

In collaboration with *Alexander Krull* (University of Birmingham, UK), a researcher in the field and external to the AI4Life consortium, we assembled a set of paired microscopy datasets covering a range of biological samples and imaging conditions. The challenge runs from June through August 2025. Submissions are packaged as Docker containers and evaluated automatically on a held-out test set using PSNR and SSIM metrics. As in the previous challenge, participants are encouraged to release their code publicly, with mandatory sharing required for the top three entries.

2.2.2.2 Challenge results

The challenge attracted 16 registrants from 10 countries and received 45 total submissions. As of 31.08.2025 the challenge had not reached its allocated budget and therefore remains open for continued participation.

2.2.3. Challenge 3: Denoising for Calcium Imaging

2.2.3.1 Challenge description

The challenge can be found using this link - <https://ai4life-cidc25.grand-challenge.org/>.

The third AI4Life Challenge focused on calcium imaging denoising, a problem of particular importance in neuroscience, where researchers use genetically encoded calcium indicators (GECI) to track cellular activity in living tissue. Calcium imaging data is both spatially and temporally structured, and effective denoising methods must preserve the fine dynamics of neuronal signals while removing noise that obscures biological information.

In collaboration with *Xinyang Li* (Tsinghua University, China), a well-known expert in the field and external to the AI4Life consortium, we designed synthetic calcium imaging datasets in which the ground truth activity is precisely known and noise can be added in a controlled, realistic way. This approach allows us to evaluate algorithms with high accuracy across different noise regimes, sample morphologies, and imaging conditions, while also enabling participation from both supervised and unsupervised method developers. The challenge opened in July 2025 and will run until August 2025, with submissions packaged in Docker containers and evaluated automatically using both spatial and temporal quality metrics: spatial Signal to Noise Ratio and temporal Signal to Noise Ratio.

2.2.3.2 Challenge results

The challenge attracted 17 registrants from 7 countries and received 46 total submissions. As of 31.08.2025 the challenge had not reached its allocated budget and therefore remains open for continued participation.

3. Conclusion

The AI4Life Challenges demonstrated a practical way to bridge the life sciences and their image analysis problems with the global AI and computer vision community to bring value to both fields. While our initial idea of sourcing challenges directly from Open Call submissions proved impractical due to below-expectation data readiness of OC projects and lack of sufficiently general OC projects, the adapted strategy, focusing on broadly relevant denoising tasks, produced well-scoped, impactful challenges with good community participation.

Key achievements include:

- Establishing reproducible, openly accessible benchmarks for both supervised and unsupervised denoising in fluorescence microscopy and calcium imaging.
- Leveraging existing and synthetic datasets to enable precise evaluation.
- Attracting international participation from researchers in both biological imaging and AI/computer vision.
- Building technical and organisational workflows for future challenges, including documentation, starter code, and support structures.

The experience reinforces the importance of sustained engagement with both data providers and algorithm developers to ensure that challenges are scientifically relevant, computationally tractable, and of benefit to a wider scientific community of potential users.

This being said, the three presented Challenges can only be a beginning, and we strongly advocate for continued creation of similar challenges on other relevant analysis tasks. While the AI4Life project funding is nearing its end, our team will be happy to support others who are interested in creating their own public challenge for our communities.

